

Primer: Principles of Data Visualization

Marianna Rosso, Leonhard Held
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What is a data visualization and why does it matter?

Data visualization refers to the graphical representation of data in a visual format, such as charts, graphs and maps, in order to facilitate the understanding, analysis, and communication of complex information (Wilke, 2019). It plays a vital role in academia as it enables researchers and students to effectively explore, interpret, and present even large volumes of data. Transforming data into visual representations simplifies complex concepts, reveals patterns, trends, and relationships, and enhances data-driven decision-making processes. Effective data visualizations can aid in identifying correlations and outliers, facilitating hypothesis formulation, supporting research findings and providing insights, and enabling impactful communication of research outcomes to a wider audience. All visualizations in the present Primer were generated in R from data publicly available [here](#). The code is available [here](#).

Basics of visual grammar

In order to construct an effective data visualization, the first step is to become familiar with the type and collection purpose of the data. Specifically, one needs to clarify **what question the data is supposed to answer**. Several tools can be used to understand what types of visualizations are advised for the different types of data (for example, visit [this](#) online tool). Secondly, one needs to **pinpoint the audience**. For instance, the data visualizations displayed in a public presentation may be different than the ones reported in a scientific publication. The final step is to **align the audience and the visualization**. For this, five inter-linked principles of data visualization are discussed below: preattentive attributes, aesthetics, hierarchy, economy, and honesty (Cairo, 2012; Knaflic, 2015; Leborg, 2006). We also give a list of useful resources to read more about different aspects of data visualization.

Preattentive attributes

Preattentive attributes can be processed almost immediately and can help to guide the audience through a visualization and focus their attention on specific features of a plot. In other words, they signal an audience on **where to look**. Such attributes follow a hierarchical order, starting with the most dominant attribute, *position*, which catches the eye through spatial arrangement. *Color* follows, highlighting specific elements with distinct hues. *Size* comes next, where larger or smaller elements stand out in a visual. Lastly, *shape* variations can aid in differentiation, although they may have a lower impact compared to the previous attributes. By combining these elements strategically, we can make our visuals easier to understand and navigate (Figure 1).

In visualizations, **colors** are used to distinguish between categories by using a palette or a range of distinct colors. However, it's important to limit the number of colors used in a chart to 6–8, ensuring they remain easily distinguishable. With this constraint in mind, color selection should be deliberate and purposeful (Figure 2A). For instance, in bar charts, where visual flow is crucial, the use of colors should be minimal to avoid unnecessary interruptions. Alternatively, where multiple categories need to be displayed, labels may be used (Figure 2B). On the other hand, when representing continuous data, a color gradient can be employed to signify a gradual change.

It is essential to be mindful of **color blindness** when creating visualizations. For instance, the 'colorspace' R package offers a versatile set of tools for choosing and manipulating colors and palettes,

Figure 1: **A.** Examples of preattentive attributes. The eye is drawn to the one element within each group that is different from the rest (A. color, B: size, C: shape, D: line length). **B.** Specific preattentive attributes are used here to draw the attention to those laboratories that have higher or lower values (line length), the relationship of the mean values to a certain threshold (color), and the use of different study protocols (transparency). Here, a bar chart is used as it is ideal to display summary values, in this case, mean outcomes, across categories.

aligning well with the human visual system for intuitive palette selection (Zeileis et al., 2020).

Figure 2: **A.** A lollipop chart utilizing a color scheme to distinguish between treatment and control groups. This approach is particularly crucial in maintaining a visual flow. This chart is ideal to display the difference in summary measures of two groups (treatment vs. control), across categories (Labs). **B.** In cases where multiple categories need representation, color differentiation is applied to represent different laboratories, as well as labels, to enhance clarity. Here, a line chart is ideal to represent a trend over time or over sequential categories.

Aesthetics

Aesthetically pleasing visualizations are not only perceived as more appealing, but also more readily accepted and used over time. Viewers spend more time on attractive graphics, enhancing their memory retention. Consequently, the intended message may have a lasting impact. In presentations or posters, employing diverse plots for different outcomes helps the audience remember them accurately and avoids confusion. Pleasing aesthetics can be achieved by using consistent color schemes, fonts, and text alignment (Figure 3A).

Hierarchy

Whenever a hierarchical structure is present in the study design or in the data to be displayed, such hierarchy should be made clear to the audience. For instance, this can be achieved with Sankey plots (in which the width of the lines is proportional to the quantity of a specific property, Figure 3B).

Figure 3: **A** The circular heatmap, chosen for its enhanced visual appeal, provides a captivating representation of the data. A heatmap is ideal to display the distribution or intensity of values across two dimensions. **B**. The Sankey plot effectively portrays the distribution of specific proportions across classes, allowing for clear visualization of hierarchical structures.

Economy

De-cluttering a visualization by removing all features that can be removed allows the message to be straightforward without distracting or creating interruptions in the viewer’s eye. The data/ink ratio prompts the designer to, within reason, erase *non-data-ink*, referring to those elements that don’t add information (e.g. grid lines, colors without meaning or purpose, etc.), and erase redundant *data-ink*. This includes for instance unnecessary labels, excessive information unrelated to the visualization’s message, and others (Figure 4).

Figure 4: By removing the grey background and the redundant legend while keeping the essential axis references, as well as introducing a slight transparency, the visualization is clearer and less distracting. In the figures, a beeswarm plot accompanies a boxplot. Such visualization is ideal when comparing continuous data amongst two or more categories.

Honesty

Honesty in data visualization involves refraining from manipulations or aiming to reduce biases, for instance, by presenting raw data alongside summary statistics. This also extends to axis scaling and labelling, avoiding distortions that can mislead interpretations (Figure 5). Honest visualizations enable viewers to access the complete picture, evaluate nuances within the dataset, and make accurate comparisons. They empower individuals to critically analyze the data, comprehend its scope, and assess potential biases. Ultimately, honesty in data visualization promotes integrity, reliability, and a more meaningful understanding of the underlying information (Jambor et al., 2021; Weissgerber et al., 2015).

Figure 5: **A.** Boxplot alone can be deceiving as they don't take into account the amount of raw data displayed. In the figure, the same boxplots are generated with both a large and a small sample size. Here, a jitter plot is a type of scatter plot used to display the full distribution of a set of numerical data points. **B.** and **C.** show the importance of taking into account the axis scaling, as a difference between two groups may appear much larger (**B**) or smaller (**C**). Here, error bars accompany bar charts, and are ideal to visualize summary statistics, such as the standard deviation, in two or more groups.

References

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Resources

Below, a list of further readings for each element of visualization as discussed above, indexed as follows. **1:** preattentive attributes, **2:** use of color, **3:** aesthetic, **4:** hierarchy, **5:** economy, **6:** honesty.

Books

- Andrews, R. J., *Info we trust: How to inspire the world with data*, John Wiley Sons, 2019 (**3**)
- Bremer, Nadieh; Wu, Shirley, *Data Sketches: A journey of imagination, exploration, and beautiful data visualizations*, CRC Press, 2021 (**2,3**)
- Cairo, Alberto, *The Functional Art: An introduction to information graphics and visualization*, New Riders, 2012 (**1,2,4,5,6**)

- Cairo, Alberto, *How charts lie: Getting smarter about visual information*, WW Norton Company, 2019 **(1,2,4,5,6)**
- Drucker, Johanna, *Graphesis: Visual forms of knowledge production*, Harvard University Press Cambridge, 2014 **(1,3,4)**
- Drucker, Johanna, *Visualization and interpretation: Humanistic approaches to display*, MIT Press, 2020 **(1,2,3)**
- Healy, Kieran, *Data visualization: a practical introduction*, Princeton University Press, 2018 **(1,2,3,6)**,
- Knaflic, Cole Nussbaumer, *Storytelling with data: A data visualization guide for business professionals*, John Wiley Sons, 2015 **(1,2,3,4,5)**
- Leborg, Christian, *Visual Grammar*, Princeton Architectural Press, 2006 **(1,2,3,4,5)**
- Matei, Sorin Adam; Hunter, Lucas, *Data storytelling is not storytelling with data: A framework for storytelling in science communication and data journalism*, Taylor Francis, 2021 **(3,6)**
- McCandless, David, *Knowledge is beautiful*, HarperCollins, 2014 **(3)**
- McCandless, David, *The visual miscellaneum: a colorful guide to the world's most consequential trivia*, Collins Design New York, 2009 **(2,3)**
- Tufte, Edward R., *The visual display of quantitative information*, Graphics Press, 2001 **(1,2,3,4,5,6)**
- Tufte, Edward R., *Beautiful evidence*, Graphics press Cheshire, CT, 2006 **(2,3,4,5,6)**
- Tufte, Edward R.; McKay, Susan R.; Christian, Wolfgang; Matey, James R., *Visual explanations: Images and quantities, evidence and narrative*, American Institute of Physics, 1998 **(2,3,5,6)**

Websites

- [Best Practices for Data Visualisation - Royal Statistical Society](#) **(1,2,3,4,5,6)**
- [Color palette generator](#) **(2)**
- [Color palette simulator](#) **(2)**
- [HCL Color Space generator](#) **(2)**
- [Two Simple Steps to Create Colorblind-Friendly Data Visualizations](#) **(2)**

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Edited by Marianna Rosso ([0000-0002-1236-4085](#)) and Leonhard Held ([0000-0002-8686-5325](#)).